

Electrochemical Behaviour of Substituted-*N*-aryl-*N*'-2-(4-*p*-anisyl-5-arylazothiazolyl)thiocarbamides

A. RAMESH and J. KRISHNAMACHARYULU

Department of Chemistry, J.N.T.U. College of Engineering, Anantapur-515 002
and

L. K. RAVINDRANATH* and S. BRAHMAJI RAO

Department of Chemistry, S. K. University, Anantapur-515 003

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N-Aryl-*N*'-2-(4-*p*-anisyl-5-arylazothiazolyl)thiocarbamides (1-5) exhibit a well-defined reduction wave at DME and a cathodic peak at HMDE in Britton-Robinson buffers (pH 2.0-10.0) containing 60% (v/v) dimethylformamide. The products of electrolysis have been characterised and a plausible mechanism has been suggested.

LITERATURE survey¹ reveals that electrochemical behaviour of thiazolylazo compounds are limited.

Because of this paucity of the information on electrochemical behaviour and in view of the usefulness of these compounds as good arperometric reagents for metal analysis besides their medicinal use, the authors have taken up a detailed study on the electrochemical behaviour of some *N*-aryl-*N*'-2-(4-*p*-anisyl-5-arylazothiazolyl)thiocarbamides (1-5) at DME and HMDE and the results are communicated here.

- 1 ; R=3-CH₃, R¹=3-Cl
- 2 ; R=3-OCH₃, R¹=4-OCH₃
- 3 ; R=3-CH₃, R¹=2-OC₂H₅
- 4 ; R=3-OCH₃, R¹=4-CH₃
- 5 ; R=3-Cl, R¹=4-CH₃

Experimental

The substituted-*N*-aryl-*N*'-2-(4-*p*-anisyl-5-arylazothiazolyl)thiocarbamides (1-5) were prepared by coupling the substituted aryl diazonium salts with 2-amino-4-anisylthiazole and then condensing the product with substituted arylisothiocyanates by the reported method². The purity of the compounds was checked up by tlc. Polarograms and cyclic voltammograms of the compounds were recorded in Britton-Robinson buffers (pH 2.0-10.0) containing 60%(v/v) dimethylformamide. The equipments used and the experimental details are similar to those reported earlier³.

Results and Discussion

Polarography: Compounds 1-5 exhibited a single reduction wave in the entire pH range of study (Table 1). The linear dependence of the limiting current (i_a) on square-root of mercury column height (\sqrt{h}) and the low temperature coefficient (1.0-1.6% K⁻¹) of the limiting current suggest the diffusion-controlled nature of the wave. Semilogarithmic analysis of the wave ($E_{1/2}$ vs $\log(i_a - i)/i$ plots) and the shift in $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential with the increase in concentration of the depolariser suggests that the wave is irreversible. The low $K_{f,h}^0$ (heterogeneous rate constant) values and the high ΔG^* (activation free energy) values too lead to the same conclusion. α_n (transfer coefficient), ΔG^* , $K_{f,h}^0$ and P (number of protons) values are calculated by the usual procedures⁴ (Table 2).

The millicoulometric studies were carried out by the reported method⁵ using a mercury pool cathode for determining the number of electrons (n). The value of n was determined using the formula,

$$n = n_1 \left(\frac{\Delta i_a \text{ Cad}}{i_a \text{ Cad}} \right) \left(\frac{i_a \text{ sub}}{\Delta i_a \text{ sub}} \right) \left(\frac{V_1 C_1}{V_2 C_2} \right)$$

where i_a and Δi_a values are the diffusion current and the change in the diffusion current of the polarograms obtained when the experimental solution is subjected to polarography, and n_1 and n are the number of electrons involved in the reduction of cadmium ions and the substrate respectively. The value of n is found to be 4 by comparison with CdSO₄.

Cyclic voltammetry: Cyclic voltammograms showed a single cathodic peak in the forward scan. However no anodic peak is observed in the reverse scan. This suggests irreversible behaviour of the compounds. This is further supported by the negative

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH ON $E_{1/2}$ AND WAVE-HEIGHT OF COMPOUNDS 1-5

pH	$-E_{1/2}$ (V) vs SCE					Wave-height (μA)				
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
2.0	0.36	0.46	0.44	0.39	0.39	5.9	5.7	5.3	5.9	5.7
3.0	0.43	0.53	0.52	0.47	0.44	5.5	5.7	5.0	5.5	5.3
4.0	0.49	0.60	0.59	0.56	0.50	5.3	5.4	4.8	5.1	4.9
5.0	0.55	0.69	0.66	0.63	0.59	4.9	5.0	4.5	4.8	4.9
6.0	0.62	0.75	0.72	0.69	0.66	4.7	5.0	4.5	4.8	4.9
7.0	0.66	0.81	0.76	0.74	0.70	4.7	4.9	4.8	4.8	4.9
8.0	0.73	0.87	0.79	0.77	0.77	4.7	4.9	4.8	4.9	4.9
9.0	0.73	0.87	0.79	0.77	0.77	4.7	4.9	4.8	4.9	4.9
10.0	0.73	0.87	0.79	0.77	0.77	4.7	4.9	4.8	4.9	4.9

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPOUNDS 1-5

pH	$K_{f,h}$ values				
	1	2	3	4	5
2.0	7.56×10^{-3}	3.76×10^{-4}	4.67×10^{-4}	2.70×10^{-4}	1.24×10^{-4}
4.0	7.20×10^{-3}	4.54×10^{-5}	4.20×10^{-5}	1.36×10^{-5}	9.30×10^{-6}
6.0	7.13×10^{-3}	6.10×10^{-6}	3.30×10^{-6}	2.60×10^{-7}	1.33×10^{-8}
8.0	4.49×10^{-6}	4.45×10^{-7}	1.04×10^{-7}	1.50×10^{-8}	8.38×10^{-9}
10.0	4.49×10^{-6}	4.45×10^{-7}	1.04×10^{-7}	1.50×10^{-8}	8.38×10^{-9}
ΔG^* values					
2.0	51 869	55 901	56 443	55 087	53 130
4.0	57 529	62 149	61 947	64 902	58 123
6.0	63 277	68 667	67 068	72 296	64 842
8.0	67 896	73 661	70 008	76 702	69 462
10.0	67 896	73 561	70 008	76 702	69 462
α_n values					
2.0	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43
4.0	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43
6.0	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43
8.0	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43
10.0	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43
P values					
	0.44	0.54	0.47	0.58	0.51

shift in the peak potentials with increasing sweep rate. The cyclic voltammetric reduction at HMDE is shown to be diffusion-controlled in the pH range 2.0–7.0 from linear plots obtained between i_p and $\nu^{1/2}$ passing through the origin. As mentioned earlier, a cathodic peak is observed during the anodic cycle instead of an anodic peak in the pH range 2.0–6.0 (Fig. 1). These peaks are known as inverted peaks. Such peaks were reported for many organic compounds in the literature⁶⁻⁸.

The inverted peaks are generally attributed to (i) the movement of mercury electrode surface due to uneven drop polarisation; this bears similarity to the approach and explanation of the polarographic maximum of the first kind⁶, and (ii) the inhibition of electrode reaction as a consequence of the coverage of the electrode by a product of the electrode reaction⁷. If the peak is traced to the second possibility, its intensity is expected to increase with decreasing sweep rate, since the build-up of the intermediate is favoured generally by decreasing sweep rate. The results in the present study do not confirm this. A significant polarographic maximum observed in the present study under the experimental conditions also confirms that the inverted peak is due to the movement of the electrode surface.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of (1) *N*-*m*-chlorophenyl-*N*'-2-(4-*p*-anisyl-5-*m*-tolylazothiazolyl)thiocarbamide (1); pH=4.0, sweep rate=100 V s⁻¹.

TABLE 3—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-5

 [Substrate] = 1×10^{-3} M, Medium : 60% dimethylformamide

Compd. no.	Sweep rate VS ⁻¹	pH=4.0				pH=8.0	
		-E _{pc} V	i _{pc} A	-E _{pinv} V	i _{pinv} A	-E _{pc} V	i _{pc} A
1	0.020	0.55	3.3	0.42	0.05	0.75	2.7
	0.050	0.56	3.7	0.43	1.30	0.76	3.1
	0.100	0.58	4.2	0.45	1.60	0.78	3.6
	0.200	0.61	5.1	0.47	2.10	0.81	4.2
2	0.020	0.63	3.5	0.49	0.90	0.92	2.5
	0.050	0.64	4.0	0.49	1.10	0.93	3.0
	0.100	0.66	4.6	0.51	1.50	0.95	3.5
	0.200	0.69	5.4	0.53	1.80	0.98	4.1
3	0.020	0.64	3.0	0.53	0.70	0.82	2.2
	0.050	0.60	3.5	0.53	0.85	0.83	2.6
	0.100	0.68	4.1	0.55	1.30	0.85	3.2
	0.200	0.71	4.8	0.58	1.60	0.88	3.8
4	0.020	0.60	3.1	0.47	0.70	0.81	2.4
	0.050	0.61	3.5	0.47	0.90	0.82	3.0
	0.100	0.63	4.0	0.48	1.30	0.84	3.4
	0.200	0.65	4.7	0.50	1.50	0.87	3.9
5	0.020	0.57	3.0	0.44	0.50	0.82	2.3
	0.050	0.58	3.5	0.44	0.75	0.83	2.8
	0.100	0.60	3.9	0.46	0.90	0.85	3.4
	0.200	0.63	4.4	0.48	1.15	0.88	4.1

Product analysis : Product analysis was done through the controlled potential electrolysis carried in a Lingane H-type cell⁸. A large pool of mercury was used as the cathode at the bottom of the larger compartment and a smaller pool of the mercury at the bottom of the smaller compartment served as the anode. The cathode compartment was filled with the solution containing 0.01M (20 ml) of compound 1, 1.0 M KCl (20 ml) and the buffer (pH 4.0; 40 ml) and the electrolysis was carried out at 0.6 V vs SCE. The number of electrons per molecule is also computed from *i-t* curves following the reported procedure⁸ and it is found to be 4. At the close of the electrolysis, 1 ml of the cell solution was withdrawn and tested for the presence of *m*-toluidine by standard spot test⁹. The remaining cell solution was partially voltatilised on a water-bath to half of its volume, allowed to cool to room temperature and the separated crystals were identified as substituted 5-aminothiazolythiocarbamides by elemental analysis and ir studies.

Mechanism : The -N-N- reductive cleavage and the reduction of the resulting imine usually occur at the same potential. Hence only a single four-electron polarographic wave or a cyclic voltammogram will be observed under the usual buffer media. Similar observations were also reported in the literature¹⁰.

Based on the observed results the following mechanism is proposed for the reduction of compounds 1-5. The mechanism is constituent with the mechanisms suggested earlier for the reduction of similar azo compounds¹¹.

where, R'' and R''' are substituted benzene and thiazoles.

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